

Association between falls, fear of falling and depressive symptoms in community-dwelling older adults

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RESUMO:

Background: The increase in longevity poses challenges to public health, particularly in managing falls and their psychological impacts on the older people. Despite this, there is scant evidence on the relationship between fear of falling (FOF), previous falls, and depressive symptoms among community-dwelling older adults. **Objective:** To evaluate the association between falls, FOF, and depressive symptoms in community-dwelling older adults. **Methods:** This is a cross-sectional study with 400 older adults attended at a Basic Health Unit in São Paulo, Brazil. The Geriatric Depression Scale (GDS) and the International Falls Efficacy Scale (FES-I) were used, supplemented by self-report questionnaires on fall history. Linear regression was employed to analyze the relationships between variables. **Results:** The mean age was 75.23 (SD=8.53) years, with 63.2% being female. Depressive symptoms were observed in 18.3% of the participants, while 90.5% reported fear of falling (FOF). More than half (63%) experienced falls, with 49.5% occurring in the last year. Factors such as female gender, negative health perception, and functional dependence were associated with depressive symptoms. Adjusted analyses indicated that both fear of falling (FOF) (B=0.043; p=0.012) and history of falls (B=0.725; p=0.015) were associated with depressive symptoms. **Conclusion:** This study highlights the association between falls, FOF, and depressive symptoms among older people, reinforcing the need for targeted interventions to mitigate these factors and promote the mental and physical health of this population.

Palavras-chave: Aged; Depression; Falls; Fear of falling; Older people.

Organização:

Biblioteca Prof. Dr. Eurípedes Garcia

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